

Exercise 2 (Group 17) - Reproduce experimental results from a paper

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Fig. 1. ChatGPT-4o generated teaser picture with spelling mistake

This report documents the process of reproducing experiments and results from the paper Zero-Shot Recommendation as Language Modeling, focusing on evaluating GPT-based movie recommendations compared to BERT and BPR algorithms. The experimental setup was provided by the original authors. The reproducibility of the experiments was assessed. It revealed some inconsistencies and uncertainties caused by insufficient parameter descriptions. The authors encountered difficulties in fully replicating figures from the paper and the conclusions could be confirmed only partially.

CCS Concepts: • **Computing methodologies** → **Natural language generation**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: large language model, datasets, conversational recommendation

1 Introduction

This report aims to document the *reproduction of the experimental setup, the experiments and the results as explained in a scientific paper*. In case of inconsistencies, it was required to challenge the conclusions drawn. This group work was performed as part of the lecture "Experiment Design for Data Science" in the winter semester 2024/25. The objects under investigation provided by the authors of the original study have been the following:

- the paper *Zero-Shot Recommendation as Language Modeling* [1]
- the coolab notebook *lm_rec_ECIR.ipynb* (MD5= FFE6E6420C0B11F617229C0909BFCD0E)
- data file *ml-1m.zip* (MD5= C4D9EECFCA2AB87C1945AFE126590906)

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The main hypothesis: Standard GPT LM (Language Model) based movie recommendations can achieve better results than BERT NSP (Next Sentence Prediction) or BPR (Bayesian Personalized Ranking) algorithm which serves as baseline.

2 Workflow and Cooperation

The workload was divided based on the three figures presented in the paper, with the last figure consisting of three distinct components (BPR, GPT2, and BERT), resulting in five equal parts. We began by copying the provided notebook from the original paper to Google Colab, where we made the necessary modifications and extensions for each section in a minimal yet effective manner. All changes were carefully documented within the notebook itself to ensure transparency and reproducibility. The final report was written collaboratively, with each author contributing to discussions, revisions, and refinements.

3 Reproducibility

3.1 Code and datasets

The original code was easily accessible with a Colab link in the article. The original code served as a blueprint for the experimentation process, but did not include the implementation details for generating the results, such as graphs and visualizations. Consequently, we had to thoroughly understand the code structure and write our own scripts to produce and verify the outputs. Access to the data used in section 3.3 and 3.4 of the paper was possible without limitations. The filter criteria used are also well described. We could confirm the number of users (6,040), but the number of movies (3,090) is not comprehensible. `df['movieId'].nunique()` returns 3,604. However, we do not assume that this affects the results of the experiments. In the paper some parameters have been derived from the data, which we could retrace.

3.2 Reproduction Fig. 1 Comparison of different prompt structures

The algorithm for finding suitable prompt candidates is roughly described, but no code is provided. We have not reproduced the analysis of the Reddit comments, but we tried to verify the conclusion *"Our corpus-derived prompts significantly outperform..."*. We could reproduce similar results; see Fig 2. We used a one-way ANOVA for statistical testing. The p-value is 0.25 which is not less than 0.05 (our alpha value). We cannot reject the null hypothesis that all groups have the same mean. Therefore, the conclusion in the paper does not hold.

Fig. 2. Original figure versus reproduction: Comparison of LM recommendations MAP@1 with different prompt structures

3.3 Reproduction Fig. 2 Effect of the number of ratings per test user

Fig. 3. Reference: Figure 2 from the paper

Fig. 4. Reference: Figure 3 from the paper

To reproduce Figure 2, we implemented the same experiment as described in the code provided. The paper reference can be seen in Fig 7. During our analysis, we observed that the figure included a shaded region, which appeared to represent the standard deviation of the results. However, our initial test runs produced trends that differed from those in the paper, with a significantly larger standard deviation.

One major challenge was the lack of detailed information in the paper regarding user seeds, the number of runs, or the exact experimental parameters used to generate the figure. To reduce variability and obtain a more reliable reproduction, we hypothesized that the authors might have repeated the experiments either with different user seeds or by running the same experiment multiple times. Since LLM-based recommendations can yield slightly different results for the same prompt, repeating the experiment could help stabilize the standard deviation.

Figure 5 presents our reproduced results. Figure 5a shows the experiment with different user seeds and figure 5b shows the repeated experiments over 5 iterations. While we somewhat captured the overall look, we were unable to exactly match the original figure. We are getting a different line as well as a way larger standard deviation. The precise methodology used to obtain the figure remains unclear.

Fig. 5. Recreation: Figure 2

3.4 Reproduction Fig. 3 Comparison with matrix factorization and NSP

3.4.1 *Fig. 3 BPR baseline* As baseline, the paper opts for the Bayesian Personalized Ranking (BPR) algorithm [2], with the implementation from the library cornac ([3]).

While the authors cite the paper of the library, they neither provide any implementation details on how they used it nor specify a version of the library. A given link (<https://cornac.readthedocs.io/en/latest/models.html#bayesian-personalized-ranking-bpr>) to the API references is broken, however we were able to find the likely corresponding updated link (https://cornac.readthedocs.io/en/latest/api_ref/models.html#bayesian-personalized-ranking-bpr).

The cornac library has a class BPR, that can directly be initialized with the hyperparameters that were given in the paper. After initialization, a train and test method (`fit()`, `score()`) can be called directly on the corresponding data without requiring any further information.

As evaluation metric, the authors select MAP@1, which they shortly explain, and refer to the original paper of the metric [4]. Again, they do not specify an implementation. The cornac method for MAP doesn't allow specifying a parameter k . As the implementation is straightforward, we chose to implement the metric from scratch.

While the basic use of these methods is reasonably clear, major uncertainties arise when trying to recreate the entire experiment.

The most uncertain part is the preparation of the data. The notebook provided focuses only on the experiments with the language models that require the data in the form of prompts and return text. BPR, on the other hand, requires tuples of users, movies and ratings and outputs scores for each user-film tuple in test sets. We implement processing of the data according to the details provided in section 3.1 of the paper: (1.) We filter all ratings $r \in [2.5, 4.0]$, and consider $r < 2.5$ as negative and $r > 4.0$ as positive. (2.) We keep 20% of the users for the test set. (3.) Trainset: All ratings for train-users + max 5 positive ratings of test users + max 10 negative ratings of test users (for this last point, no information was given in the paper). (4.) Testset: 4 negative ratings + 1 positive rating for test users. As a last assumption, we plot the standard error to recreate the shadow from the original plot, which is not described by the authors.

Fig. 6. Recreation: BPR baseline & increasing train set

It is notable that the results do not align with those reported in the paper. For increasing number of users in the training set, the model's performance doesn't get better, but pendles in at 0.21 ± 0.02 . According to the method of evaluation, this is equal to a random guess.

In the paper, BPR is used as a baseline and therefore not the main focus of research. It is believed to be a well-known method, representative for state-of-the-art models. However, without further implementation details, we have neither been able to improve the results nor reproduce the increasing trend as shown in the original plot.

3.4.2 *Fig. 3 GPT2 base and medium* We conducted experiments with GPT-2-base (referred to as "gpt2" in the graphs below) and GPT-2-medium ("gpt2-medium" in the graphs below) to replicate and verify the findings from the original paper. In the first experiment, we varied the number of test users (1, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500) while keeping all other parameters at their default values. The evaluation metric used was the mean Precision@1, calculated across multiple runs with different numbers of test users.

Our results show a mean Precision@1 of 0.30 ± 0.10 for GPT-2-base and 0.35 ± 0.11 for GPT-2-medium. While these results do not exactly replicate the original findings, the observed discrepancies remain within the expected margin of error. This indicates that the reproduced experiment is broadly consistent with the original study. Figure 7 illustrates the findings with varying numbers of test users.

Fig. 7. GPT-2 base & medium with varying users

Fig. 8. GPT-2 base & medium with different parameters

In addition to the replication study, we conducted further experiments with GPT-2-base and GPT-2-medium by varying specific parameters, including prompts and user offsets, while fixing the number of test users. These modifications yielded mean Precision@1 scores of 0.34 ± 0.03 for GPT-2-base and 0.39 ± 0.03 for GPT-2-medium. The results align closely with those reported in the original study, reinforcing the validity of the replication. Figure 8 provides a detailed visualization of the experiments with different parameter configurations.

3.4.3 *Fig. 3 BERT and variations*

We also performed experiments using BERT-base-uncased and BERT-large-uncased models to replicate and validate the findings from the original paper. The number of test users was varied (1, 50, 100, 200, 300, 400, 500), and seeds for NumPy and PyTorch operations were set to ensure reproducibility. However, minor variations in outputs were observed upon re-running the experiment, highlighting stochastic elements in the model's behavior.

Fig. 9. BERT base & large with varying users

Fig. 10. BERT base & large with different parameters

Our results yielded a mean Precision@1 of 0.18 ± 0.06 for BERT-base NSP and 0.19 ± 0.06 for BERT-large NSP, as shown in Fig. 9. While these results are not identical to those in the original paper, they align within the general findings.

In addition, we evaluated BERT (base and large) models with various configurations and compared them with RoBERTa (base and large) and DistilBERT (base-cased and base-uncased) for a comprehensive analysis. See figures 10, 11 and 12.

Fig. 11. RoBERTa - different configurations

Fig. 12. DistilBERT - different configurations

By varying prompts and user offsets while keeping the number of test users constant, we assessed the models' precision. Among these, BERT-large achieved the highest mean Precision@1 of 0.25 ± 0.03 , while RoBERTa-large and DistilBERT base-uncased both scored 0.20 ± 0.02 . All models exhibited precision within the range of 0.18 to 0.25, but were outperformed by GPT-based models.

4 Conclusions

The reproduction of the experiments was partially successful, but required significant effort due to missing implementation details and inconsistencies in data filtering. While the data set and core parts of the code were available, key parameters, such as the number of runs for stabilizing results and the seed values, were not specified. The BPR baseline was only referenced as a library without version details or clear usage instructions, requiring us to re-implement parts of the evaluation. We had to recreate the visualizations while making assumptions about the meaning of the uncertainty shadows.

Despite these challenges, some findings aligned with the original paper, but overall reproducibility was limited. This raises concerns about the robustness of its conclusions. Any description of significance tests is missing in the paper and the code provided.

References

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